

Cohesion and Adhesion in High Polymers

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Recent developments in polymers show that they are in a position to replace metals, particularly for articles of light weight, if their services are rendered in the temperature range between 50 and 300°.

Organic polymers of tensile strength upto 500,000 p.s.i. can be made possible. Quality steels are still about four to five times stronger; but if one compares the strength on the basis of equal weight, the polymers can ever be superior to metal since their specific gravity is much less in comparison to the metals.

If we analyse the situation since the introduction of the synthetic polymers, we would observe that the two principal factors which lead to superior mechanical strength of polymers are: (i) introduction of new materials with new chemical compositions, and (ii) improvement of the molecular organisation of the given material. Although the rayon tire cord still consists of the same cellulose, the higher tensile strength of the material has been achieved due to the higher molecular weight and better molecular and fibrillar organisation of the product. The improved impact strength of polystyrene has been accomplished by the introduction of additional monomer-acrylonitrile or butadiene or both-so that the new materials consist of a copolymer of two or more individual ingredients.

It has been realised that natural products used as adhesives by our ancestors are polymeric in nature; in fact most adhesives used at present are polymers of one sort or another.

MOLECULAR weight of a polymeric material is one of the most important factors which help to increase its cohesive strength. For linear polymers, a general relationship exists between mechanical properties such as bending, tensile strength, resistance against tear or abrasion and molecular weight or degree of polymerisation. The relationship (between strength and degree of polymerisation (DP) can be expressed in the form: ¹⁻⁸

$$TS = TS_{\infty} - \frac{C}{DP_n} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where TS = Tensile strength at the degree of polymerisation DP_n .

TS_{∞} = Tensile strength at infinitely high DP.

C = a constant characteristic for the given polymer.

DP_n = number average degree of polymerisation.

Another principal factor which influences the mechanical behaviour of a polymer is its molecular organisation. Polymeric materials consist of long, flexible chains which can either be randomly entangled or laterally ordered. If the chains are all parallel to a certain axis, their lateral attachment will be better than if they are arranged at random in space; the axial orientation of the individual macromolecule improves the lateral attachment. If the macromolecular chains have a very regular structure, they will be able to form bundles of a high degree of lateral order, which resemble very small crystallites inside of which there is a firm and dense system of stress transferring macromolecules. The possibility to establish chemi-

cal cross-links between the individual chains to increase their lateral attachment by strong localised bonds also exists.

A third factor of great importance for the mechanical performance of all polymeric systems is the super-molecular uniformity of their structure and texture. During the process of solidification of a polymer from a solution or from a melt, the molecular chains are oriented and crystallised with the formation of a highly anisotropic system of parallel bundles with varying length and thickness, and there is every chance of the formation of super-molecular cracks or crevices, which act as centres of stress accumulation. The strength of polymer is thus much lower than the theoretical value, which proves that weak spots play a decisive role in the mechanical behaviour of such materials.

The importance of weak spots for the mechanical strength of materials was put on a quantitative theoretical basis by the studies of Griffith and Rowan^{4,5}. The aspects presented in the work made it clear that not only cohesive but also adhesive bonds would be affected in their strength by weak spots or weak layers.

The quantitative analysis of cohesive strength in the field of polymers reveals that the energy necessary to dissociate covalent bonds of the type -C-O-C-N-associated with polyester, celluloses polyamides is of the order of 80-90 Kcal/mole. For hydrogen bonds and van der Waals forces that exist between the individual macromolecules and are responsible for the important properties like melting point and solubility, the energy values per mole are

* Dedicated with abiding adoration to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee on the occasion of the celebration of his sixty-fifth birth anniversary.

6 Kcal and 2 Kcal respectively. Quantitative studies of the progressive degradation of the macromolecules in ultrasonic fields^{6,7} confirm that the strength of the single bond between carbon, oxygen and nitrogen is around 5×10^{-4} dynes per bond, which is of the same order as the value mentioned before.

Effect of temperature on the properties of polymers :

It is the temperature and the time for which heat is applied that have the most important effect on the adhesive and cohesive properties of polymers.

Due to their length and to the excessive energy of the bonds between individual macromolecules, thermal motion of the whole macromolecule is not feasible, because the energy necessary to achieve this would probably destroy the chemical bond of the chain. The increased thermal energy, therefore, causes successive movements of individual chain sections, which are similar to the thermal motion. The chain molecules continue to change their shapes incessantly ; they fold, coil and uncoil depending on accidental thermal shocks against different sections of the chain. The size of these sections-segments-as kinetically independent sections of the macromolecule, determines the flexibility of the whole chain macromolecule.

The mechanical properties of long chain and branched polymers depend markedly on the temperature. The course of their deformation in relation to the temperature, which is expressed by the so called thermomechanical curves, defines the regions of their transition states (glass-like, elastic and plastic). The temperature intervals of the vitrifications (T_g), i.e., glass transition temperature and of

Fig. 1. Deformation of plastics with rise of temperature.

the transition from the plastic state into the elastic state (T_t) are the most important factors in the assessment of adhesive and cohesive properties (Fig.-1). Favourable conditions for good adhesive properties are given in the plastic region, i.e., above T_t or above the second order transition temperature. The temperature affects markedly the mobility of the segments and consequently the fluidity of the polymer in the plastic state. This effect is analogous to that of softeners and low molecular weight resins.

Like the effect of increased temperature, solvents too, loosen the bonds between macromolecules and increase their mobility.

However, in polymers changes of two kinds can take place during thermal stresses. They are : mechanical changes, and chemical changes. Depending on the environment, the temperature range and the period for which heat is applied, changes in mechanical properties take place ; with thermoplastics the changes are often reversible. If, however, the polymer is allowed to remain at a higher temperature for a longer time, chemical changes may occur which are irreversible.

In simple substances, the melting process is determined by a rather sharp phase transition-solid to liquid or vice versa. It takes place at an exactly defined temperature and it is typical of every simple substance. In the transition of the polymer from the partly crystalline state to the amorphous state, the characteristic physical properties of the polymer, its structure and thermodynamic parameters are subject to changes similar to those of simple substances in the course of melting, i.e., in the transition of the low-molecular substance into the liquid state. The melting process is accompanied by volume and heat content changes. An exact determination of the phase transition in polymers is, however, rather difficult due to the fact that not the whole macromolecule but only its segments take part in the crystallisation process. If the phase change were to take place at an exact temperature the polymer crystals would have to be large enough to allow the effect of the free surface energy to be reduced to a minimum. As this condition cannot be fulfilled the melting process occurs within a wide temperature range. Small and imperfect crystals melt at a lower temperature than large crystals.

With increasing degree of orientation in polymers the strength increases while the elongation decreases. At a higher degree of orientation the tension between the macromolecules is more evenly distributed, nevertheless their freedom of motion is diminished. It results therefrom that it is adequate elasticity and elongation rather than a strength exceeding the given optimum that we require of adhesives. The mobility of the macromolecules can be readily obtained in the non-oriented region, i.e. in the region above the vitrification temperature.

Adhesion and Adhesives

Although Sir Isaac Newton wrote in his Opticks two and one-half centuries ago that "there are agents in nature able to make the particles of joints stick together by very strong attraction and it is the business of experimental philosophy to find them out", any real progress that has been made in understanding the forces operating in adhesion was only within the last few decades.

The effort to apply modern concepts to adhesion was accelerated in the early 1950s by the excellent work of Bowden and Tabor⁸, De Bruyne⁹, and many others. In the 1940s and early 1950s, some truly inspirational work by Zisman was directly applicable to the concepts of adhesion. The first of these efforts¹⁰ relating to surface-energy concepts is of prime importance in understanding adhesion phenomena. Work of Derjaguin¹¹, Voyutskii¹², Bikermann¹³ and Vasenin¹⁴ has helped considerably for a better understanding of the principles underlying the phenomena of adhesives and adhesion.

An adhesive is a material, according to ASTM description, capable of holding materials together by surface attachment. This capability, however, is not an intrinsic property of the substance; it is developed only under certain conditions while interacting with an adherend. Adherend is the term, coined by De Bruyne, for solid bonded by adhesives; it is used throughout the industry. A more general and older term is substrate. By this is meant any (mostly) solid body serving as a mechanical support of surface layers, eg., coating, films or adhesives. Adhesion is the joining together of two dissimilar materials—adhesive molecules and adherend molecules, whereas cohesion is the joining together of similar materials. Hence the adhesive bond is the bond across the adhesive-adherend interface, and the cohesive strength is the strength of the main mass of the adhesive itself.

It was realised during the thirties of this century that the natural products like mucilage, casein, albumin used as adhesives by our ancestors are polymeric in nature. Later it was also noted that adhesives with improved properties, based upon the synthetic polymers, were made possible. The improved performance as well as the versatility of these polymers have brought about a better understanding of the principles underlying the phenomenon of adhesion.

Forces operative in adhesion phenomenon :

When we study adhesion and cohesion it is realised that the forces operating across the bulk of the adhesive and across the adhesive interface must be those responsible for physical and chemical bonding. The forces that link atoms together (chemical bonding) and the forces that link molecules together (physical bonding) both are to be considered. The joining of atoms to form molecules can give rise to chemical bonds mainly of three types, namely, electrovalent, covalent and metallic. Apart from the chemical bonds there is a class of forces responsible for most of the physical properties of the compounds. These are weak attractive forces which result from the stray fields associated with polarised covalent bonds. The weak attractive physical force is referred to as van der Waals force. Clearly with molecules we can recognise two types of attractive

forces: that between two adjacent molecules is referred to as vander Waals intermolecular force, whereas that associated with the same molecule referred to as intramolecular force.

vander Waals force has been generally classified into three categories: Debye force, Keesom force and London force.

Keesom force results from the interaction of two permanent dipoles. A dipole results whenever a covalent bond is formed by the unequal sharing of the electron pairs that go to make up the bond. With this unequal sharing of the electron pair, there results in a displacement of the electron clouds and a dipole is formed. Many examples of permanent dipoles are available in organic molecules, and these are of extreme importance in considering adhesives and adhesive action. Particular examples of them are bonds formed from carbon and oxygen, carbon and nitrogen, carbon and halogen etc.

The Debye force results from the interaction of a permanent dipole with a bond system capable of being polarised. Several systems are capable of being polarised, especially carbon-carbon bonds.

London force often termed dispersion force, results from the polarisation of one molecule by another due to the oscillation of electron clouds.

The magnitude of these force is from 0 to 10 Kcal/g mole per interaction. The energy E associated with these forces is as follows :

For Keesom force,

$$E \propto \frac{\mu^4}{r^6} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where μ is the dipole moment of the permanent dipole, and r is the distance it is operating over.

For Debye force,

$$E \propto \frac{\mu^2}{r^6} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

It can be seen that whenever the dipole moment is greater than unity, Keesom force is of greater energy than Debye force, and that both diminish rapidly with increasing distance of separation of the dipoles. In fact, Debye force contributes very little to the total energy of adhesion or cohesion.

For London force,

$$E = \frac{3}{4} hV_0 (\alpha^2/r^6) \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where h is Planck's constant, α is the polarisability of the molecule, V_0 is the zero-point frequency of

the electron cloud. and r is the distance over which the force operates. This energy increases with increasing molecular size, and hence explains the very cohesive strength of polymers with high molecular weights.

Of the forces the polar or Keesom force and the dispersion or London force are by far the most important. It has been calculated that even for a molecule such as polyethylene, the London force is strong enough to provide adhesion to metals.

Nature of Interaction at the Interface between adhesive and adherend :

Direct covalent links between the adhesive and adherend, although they are rare, may be present across the interface between the two. There may also be interaction between the adhesive and a surface oxide or some layer different from the main bulk of the adherend. These direct covalent bonds give adhesion of tremendous strength. The vast majority of bonds across the adhesive adherend interface are, however, physical in nature and in this connection the importance of polar compounds, especially of Keesom force, is well recognised. For strong adhesive forces abundance of these polar groups, i.e., high polar density is needed. But it has been found that polar liquids such as nitrobenzene, ethyl alcohol and acetic acid have no power of adhesion. Hence the power of adhesion does not lie in the adhesive-adherend interface but in the main bulk of the adhesive. It has been found that the cohesive London force increases with increasing molecular weight, so that to obtain high cohesion, a high molecular weight compound is needed and high molecular weight compounds are found mainly in polymeric materials, both natural and synthetic. The presence of very high cohesive force is itself not a sure guide to a good adhesive, any more than the mere presence polar groups is also not a sure guide to a good adhesive. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) is a high molecular weight polymer with very strong cohesive forces, but due to the fluoro-carbon grouping, this material has no adhesive properties at all and in fact it is used as an anti-stick material. So it has been established that for a molecule to be a good adhesive, generally both high cohesive forces and good adhesive forces are required. Cohesive forces are generally very high in long chain or cross-linked polymers, whereas good adhesive forces are found in highly polar systems. Some of the best adhesives are formed by the *in situ* polymerisation of highly polar compounds.¹⁵

Adhesion is usually discussed in relation to the strength of joints as determined experimentally. A joint is, however, a complex system where the stresses are unlikely to be uniform. Failure occurs in the layer of the adhesive, in either component of the joint, or at either of the two interfaces between the adhesive layer and the joint component. The term adhesion should be related only to the bonding at

the interfaces, since the other two possible points of joint failure depend on the cohesive strengths of the materials involved. If it is assumed that the interfaces represent the weakest points so that the failure occurs here under stress, the strength of most joints can be explained in terms of van der Waals force alone acting at the interface. This was first pointed out long ago by de Bruyne¹⁶. He showed that relatively weak bonding at interfaces can explain experimental joint strengths, provided there is intimate contact over the entire interface.

When we deal with liquid adhesives the problem of achieving intimate molecular contact involves the wetting of the solid surface by the liquid adhesive. McBain and Hopkins¹⁷ reported that any fluid which wets a particular surface and is then converted into a tenacious mass by cooling, evaporation, solidification, polymerisation, etc. must be regarded as an adhesive for that surface. It was also pointed out that the adhesive must be able to deform during the setting process to release elastic stresses developed in the formation of a good joint¹⁸.

Surface energy and adhesion :

Although for liquid-liquid systems interfacial tensions, which can be identified with free surface energies, can be directly measured but for solid-liquid interface this is not possible. Solid-liquid interface is ill defined and less understood compared with the corresponding liquid-liquid system. To correlate adhesion with wetting, attempts have been made to explain solid-liquid system.

Fig. 2. Equilibrium of forces around a contact angle.

It is likely that most liquids wet most solids to some extent so that there is some adhesion at any liquid-solid interface. If a drop of liquid does not spread completely a state of equilibrium is assumed to arise involving a three phase point of contact between the solid, liquid and vapor phases¹⁹ (Fig. 2). Adopting the mathematical convention of treating the free surface energies as vector quantities, the well known Young equation follows :

$$\gamma_{SV} = \gamma_{SL} + \gamma_{LV} \cos\theta \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where subscripts SV, LV refer to the solid and liquid phases in equilibrium with the vapor of the liquid, and SL to the solid-liquid interface.

When $\theta > 0$ the liquid is said to be non-spreading but when $\theta = 0$ the liquid is said to wet the solid completely and to spread freely over the surface.

Dupre²⁰ showed that the reversible work of adhesion, W_A , defined as the reversible work required to separate 1 cm² of solid-liquid interface, is related to the specific free surface energies by the equation :

$$W_A = \gamma_S + \gamma_{LV} - \gamma_{SL} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where γ_S refers to the bare solid in vacuo. Thus the liquid will attach itself to the solid surface if $W_A > 0$.

A liquid in proximity to a solid can, however, produce an adsorbed vapor film on the surface and the work required to separate 1 cm² of liquid from a surface to leave such an adsorbed surface film will be,

$$W_A = \gamma_{SV} + \gamma_{LV} - \gamma_{SL} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where γ_{SV} refers to the free surface energy of the solid with the adsorbed film. Adsorption of such a vapor film involves a decrease in the free surface energy of the solid, i.e. γ_S drops to γ_{SV} . The consequent decrease in free surface energy ($\gamma_S - \gamma_{SV}$) has been termed the spreading pressure, π . The modified Young equation thus becomes,

$$\gamma_S = \pi + \gamma_{SL} + \gamma_{LV} \cos\theta \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Solids can be conveniently classified as high energy or low energy materials ; a high energy surface is one which attracts the molecules of the liquid more strongly than they attract one another, whereas a low energy surface attracts the molecules of liquid less strongly than they attract one another.

By analogy with liquid interfaces and assuming that only dispersion force operates²¹, the γ_{SL} term can be expressed as :

$$\gamma_{SL} = \gamma_S^r + \gamma_{LV} - 2(\gamma_S^d \gamma_{LV}^d)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

and by substituting for γ_{SL} in equation (4),

$$\gamma_{LV} \cos\theta = 2(\gamma_S^d \gamma_{LV}^d)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \gamma_{LV} - \pi \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

The above expression has been used to assess γ_S^d values from contact angle measurements for a series of reference hydrocarbon liquids on low-energy surfaces.

The equation (10) on rearrangement and assuming $\pi = 0$ gives the following eqn. :

$$\cos\theta = 2(\gamma_S^d)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{(\gamma_{LV}^d)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\gamma_{LV}} - 1 \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

and a plot of $\cos\theta$ vs. $(\gamma_{LV}^d)^{\frac{1}{2}}/\gamma_{LV}$ should produce a straight line with an intercept at -1 and slope $2(\gamma_S^d)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. A reasonable degree of success has been achieved for a number of such systems and typical values for γ_S^d obtained by this method are : for paraffin wax, 25.5, for polyethylene, 35 ; and for polystyrene, 44 dyne cm⁻¹ ²².

Zisman^{23,24} obtained a linear relationship between cosine of the contact angle, i.e., $\cos\theta$ and the surface tension γ_{LV} of the liquid. A plot between these two values on extrapolation to $\theta = 0$ i.e. $\cos\theta = 1$ would yield the value of the critical surface tension γ_0 of the substrate. The critical surface tension is written, γ_0 , and is the surface tension of the liquid which will just, and only just, spread on the surface with zero contact angle. Fig. 3 shows a Zisman plot for a glass surface treated with a siloxane giving $\gamma_0 = 25$ dyne cm⁻¹ ²⁵. It follows from eqn. (8) that γ_0 can only equal γ_S when both π and γ_{SL} are zero. On the very low energy surfaces such as

Fig. 3. Zisman plot for glass surface treated with Siloxane.

polyethylene and fluorocarbons, π is very small and can perhaps be ignored but γ_{SL} is not necessarily zero and may be either positive or negative or zero²⁶. In order to achieve spreading it is necessary that the critical surface tension of the solid may be equal to or greater than the surface tension of the liquid, that is,

$$\gamma_0 \geq \gamma_{LV} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

Considering the effect of presence of various groups in the hydrocarbons, it has been found that the value of γ_0 decreases as the fluorine content in a molecule increases, i.e., as the molecule becomes more closely packed²⁷ (Table 1).

Knowledge of γ_0 gives an idea about the possible wetting of polymer by a particular solvent. Sharpe and Schonhorn²⁸ have reported that the precise value of γ_0 obtained for a surface is depen-

TABLE—1

Polymer	γ (dynes/cm)
1. Polyethylene	31
2. Polyvinyl fluoride	28
3. Polyvinylidene fluoride	25
4. Polytrifluoroethylene	22
5. Polytetrafluoroethylene	18

dent upon the particular series of liquids which interact more strongly or feebly with the same surface thereby giving different values of γ .

Solubility parameter and wetting :

If the bond between adhesive and substrate is to be strong, there must be a decrease in free energy as a result of combining the two. The free energy change on mixing the two materials is :

$$\Delta F = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

where ΔH is the heat of mixing and ΔS is the entropy change. In general, when two materials interact there is an increase in entropy ; consequently, the second term on the right of the equation is negative. If we can ignore the heat of mixing term, the free energy will also be negative. This tells us the materials will tend to combine provided the heat of mixing is not too high on the positive side. We see, also, that raising the temperature makes the entropy term more negative, thus aiding the process of combination. This is particularly true when at least one of the materials being mixed or combined is a high polymer.

The heat of mixing depends on the attractive forces between adhesive and adherend. These forces may lead to either primary or secondary bonds. If the heat of mixing is zero or if it is negative as the result of hydrogen bonding or other chemical combination of adherend and adhesive, then wetting will surely be accomplished. For most nonpolar or moderately polar pairs of materials, however, the heat of mixing is positive ; consequently, the free energy will decrease only if this positive term is not too high.

Hildebrand²⁹ and others^{30,31} utilised the concept of solubility parameter, δ , to show why some pairs of materials mix more readily than others. The solubility parameter is related to the internal pressure or cohesive—energy density :

$$\delta = \left(\frac{\Delta E}{V} \right)^{1/2} \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

Where ΔE = the energy of vaporisation, and V = the molar volume.
The term, $\Delta E/V$, the energy of vaporisation per unit-volume is called the internal pressure or cohesive—energy density.

For liquids such as the fluorocarbons and hydrocarbons, this energy is very low ; therefore, low-molecular weight materials of these compositions vaporise readily.

As soon as we incorporate polar groups, we find that it requires more energy to vaporise a molecule. Thus, acetone has a higher boiling point than butane, and has a higher boiling point than butane, and isopropyl alcohol is still higher, although all three molecules are approximately of the same size and weight.

Hildebrand (loc. cit.) indicated that the greater the difference between the solubility parameters of the two materials, the greater is the heat of mixing.

$$\Delta H = V(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \phi_1 \phi_2 \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

Where V = the total volume, and ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 = the volume fractions of the respective components.

Consequently, wetting is most likely to take place when adhesive and adherend are most alike in solubility parameter.

Theories of Adhesion

Mechanical Theory :

The original theory of adhesion is the mechanical one³², which suggests that an adhesive is able to penetrate rough surfaces, and form a mechanical lock. The mechanism of penetration of a liquid into capillaries is given by the Washburn equation :

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = r\gamma \cos\theta / 4\eta h \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

Where r is the diameter of the capillary, h is the depth of penetration, γ is the surface tension of the liquid, θ is the contact angle between the solid and the liquid under investigation, and η its viscosity.

The mechanical view of adhesive action may be well typified by the layman's approach to gluing of wood. The wood is cleaned and roughened by glass-paper so that the glue may penetrate irregularities of the surface and thus get locked into it. However, the nature of interaction between glue and surface is ignored in this type of approach. The more sophisticated, but still essentially a mechanical approach, is that abrasive treatments of surfaces prior to adhesive bonding increase surface area and helps interlocking.

Adsorption theory :

Explanation of adhesion in terms of surface wetting and adsorption is usually referred to as adsorption theory of adhesion, developed by De Bruyne, McLaren and others³³⁻³⁵. According to this theory adhesion can occur in two stages.

The first stage involves the migrations of large polymer molecules from the solution to the surface of the substrate. As a result of this the polar groups of the adhesive approach polar groups of the adherend and by application of pressure and heat the chain segments of the adhesive can approach the surface more closely, even if the solvent is not present with the adhesive. The second stage consists of sorption process. When the distance between the molecules of the adhesive and substrate is less than 5 Å intermolecular forces start acting. They are (i) Attractive polar force, (ii) Induction force, and (iii) Dispersion or London force. It has been found that dispersion force is strong enough to account for the observed strength of adhesive bond, assuming that ultimate intermolecular contact is obtained at the interface. This assumption underlines the importance of wettability of surface by adhesives. Studies of Zisman²³⁻²⁵ and Sharpe and Schonhorn²⁶ on the subject of wetting confirm this point.

Diffusion theory :

A large amount of work has been done by Voyutskii²⁷⁻²⁹ and Vasenin⁴⁰. They suggest that diffusion is the main cause of the adherence of two surfaces, the term 'autohesion' being used when the two are identical chemically. The interdiffusion leads to the entanglement of the molecular chains of substrate and adhesive. They investigated the effects of time and temperature on the rates of bonding and the influences of molecular weight and chemical structure of the polymer. The view that interdiffusion in polymers does not exist has also been presented⁴¹. Anand⁴² records his opinion that diffusion takes place during autohesion but that its contribution to the bond strength seems insignificant compared with the physical adsorption brought about by van der Waals force.

Theories of adsorption and diffusion have been correlated to a large extent by Lee⁴³.

Electrostatic theory :

Several authors^{44,45} have suggested that electrostatic forces arising from the formation of an electrical double layer at the interface between the substrate and adhesive may account for adhesion. Skinner *et al.*^{46,47} while agreeing that such forces are significant, stated that they could not account for all of the observed phenomena cited in support of this theory.

Adhesives in common use

Adhesives may be classified in many ways, e.g., by mode of application and setting, chemical compositions and suitability for various substrates. However, no attempt has been made here to classify them and only polymer-based adhesives in common use are discussed in brief.

1. Soyabean and casein adhesives :

These are protein-based natural adhesives soluble in alkali. They are used mostly in the gluing of wood. Their water resistance and the quality are not up to the present standards obtained with synthetic glues. The author⁴⁸ discussed a cold-setting, quick-drying glue based on rubber latex-modified soyabean which requires a very short

TABLE—2

TEST RESULTS ON RUBBER-LATEX MODIFIED SOYABEAN GLUE BONDED PANELS, 3-PLY 4.5 MM.

Species	Dry glue shear strength of 15 × 15 F.L.G.F. cm panels kg. % after 7 (avg. of 4 samples)	Condition of 15 × 15 cm panels after 7 days soaking in water	Glue mix per sq. metre of panel g (33% S.C.)
Vateria indica (Vellapine)	97	19 Sound	630
Dipterocarpus sp. (Gurjan)	84	89 Sound	684
Mangifera indica (Mango)	84	13 Sound	608

pressing time. The dry glue shear strength and cold water resistance of the plywood bonded with the above glue are fairly satisfactory (Table-2).

2. Starch and derivatives :

Starch is the principal water-dispersible natural polymer used industrially as an adhesive. Unmodified starch pastes are prepared by stirring starch powders into water containing chlorides of zinc, calcium or magnesium until a uniform dispersion is obtained. This is used for bottle labelling and other purposes. Modified starch, like dextrin, British gum are used in carton, paste board and paper bag manufacture.

3. Polyvinyl acetate (PVA) and copolymers :

Polyvinyl acetate adhesives are used in packaging industries. They have found a place in wood bonding and is also used in book binding, gum tapes, envelopes etc. They are used as emulsions and most emulsions are stabilised with 4-5 per cent of a polyvinyl alcohol which contains about 20 per cent residual acetate groups.

4. Acrylates and methacrylates :

These two monomers are used for the production of polymers and copolymers for the adhesive industry. Their application in pressure sensitive adhesives has also been established.

5. Diacrylates and dimethacrylates :

Oxygen acts as an inhibitor of polymerisation for acrylic acid and its derivatives and prevents the formation of polymer of high molecular weight.

Anaerobic adhesives take advantage of this fact and by using ω -diacrylic esters Loctite Corporation of USA has introduced a series of liquids which, when oxygen is excluded, polymerise and cross-link because of the tetra-functional nature of the molecule.

6. *Cyanoacrylates* :

These materials set very quickly when squeezed out to thin films between many types of adherend. The monomers are liquid of very low viscosity which polymerise very easily in the presence of a surface of slight basicity having adsorbed water on it. They polymerise into polymers with physical properties depending upon the alkyl group, R. The methyl ester is one of the most widely used.

7. *Polyesters* :

Polyesters are usually formed by condensing difunctional carboxylic acids with diols. Polyethylene terephthalate and the like materials are, however, made by trans-esterification. Polyesters like alkyd resins are extensively used as paint base and also as adhesive primer on wood. Unsaturated acids are particularly used in the production of polyesters to be cross-linked by co-polymerisation with styrene and the materials, thus obtained, form the basis of glass reinforced plastics (GRP).

8. *Amino resins* :

(i) *Urea formaldehyde resin* :

It is widely used in plywood manufacture, and in the gluing of wood-based materials. Urea reacts with formaldehyde by condensation in the presence of acid or base.

By a series of reactions carried out in aqueous media, highly polymerised molecules are formed and the solution gradually thickens to syrup. The resin is used in the industry both in powder form or as a syrup. For curing, a suitable catalyst is used with the resin to modify the glue properties.

(ii) *Melamine formaldehyde resin* :

Relatively expensive melamine resin is mixed with urea formaldehyde resin to increase the water resistance of the cured glue line. For the production of decorative laminates melamine resins are widely used. Reaction between melamine and formaldehyde is believed to follow a similar mechanism to that of between urea and formaldehyde.

9. *Phenol formaldehyde resin* :

Phenol formaldehyde resins are mostly used as wood adhesives, for the production of external grade plywood. They have a limited application elsewhere, such as, in the production of metal faced block board or printed circuitry.

Phenol condenses with formaldehyde in the presence of either acid or alkali initially to form a methylol phenol and then a dimethylol phenol. During the next stage methylol groups react with further phenols to form brached structure having methylene linkage.

With acid catalyst and in the presence of deficit of formaldehyde novolak resins are formed. To complete resinification of novolak resins further formaldehyde, usually as hexamine, is added to methylolate and cross-link the resin. With alkaline catalyst and excess formaldehyde, resols are obtained. These compounds react initially to form dibenzyl ethers, which on heating lose formaldehyde and give a methylene linkage.

As wood adhesives, resorcinol formaldehyde (RF), phenol formaldehyde (PF) or PF modified RF adhesives are used for the manufacture of outdoor and tropical grades of plywood.

10. *Polyurethanes* :

They are mainly used in the foam and coating industries than in adhesives, as such. The urethane group is formed by condensation reaction of an alcohol with an isocyanate.

One part or a two-part formulation, both are used. Some one-part polyurethanes are available which are isocyanate terminated and cross-link by reaction with adsorbed moisture. The two-part adhesives comprise the prepolymer terminated in some active group and as the second part either a multifunctional isocyanate or an isocyanate terminated polymer of rather lower molecular weight. Two-part adhesives are used where high cohesive strength and improved heat resistance are required.

There is a very wide range of isocyanates and polyisocyanates available commercially. The basic isocyanates are :

Toluene di-isocyanate (TDI)
 $p-p'$ -Di-isocyanate diphenyl methane (MDI)
 $p-p'-p'$ -Tri-isocyanate triphenyl methane
 Hexamethylene di-isocyanate (HDI)

Solutions of MDI and tri-isocyanato analogue are used both before the application of polyurethane adhesives. They are also used in rubbery adhesives as a means of obtaining cross-linking at room temperatures.

11. *Rubbers* :

All rubbery polymers are used in a variety of applications, particularly where flexibility is required. Rubber can be used either as emulsions or as solvent adhesives.

Natural rubber

Latex is tapped from the tree *Hevea brasiliensis* and concentrated. Rubber combined with some tackifying resins is used in pressure sensitive adhesives, hot melt adhesives etc.

Polychloroprene

They are widely used in automobile industry, in furniture manufacture and in the shoe industry. The p-tert-butyl phenol-formaldehyde resin and magnesium oxide incorporated chloroprene rubber adhesive is remarkable for its superior temperature resistant character.

Nitrile Rubber

Nitrile rubber adhesives, being strongly polar, give better adhesion to polar adherend. Butadiene-acrylonitrile copolymer or styrene-butadiene-acrylonitrile copolymers are much in use in different industries.

12. Epoxies :

The most usual starting material for epoxy resins is bisphenol which is reacted with epichlorohydrin to give a liquid epoxy resin of moderate molecular weight. It is composed of linear molecules terminated with epoxy groups. Acid anhydrides, aromatic polyamines are known as curing agents for epoxies. Epoxy-novolak adhesives are in use.

13. Hot melt adhesives :

Hot melt adhesive is a solid at room temperature, becomes liquid when heated to temperature well over 100°C and after coming in contact with the substrate loses heat to the surface and sets. It provides the most rapid method of securing adhesion. The materials used in 'hot melt' have a low heat content and, as such, easily lose sufficient heat to solidify in seconds, if the surface to be bonded is cold. Typical hot melt composition consists of rubber, wax, a tackifying resin and some filler.

Composites

A composite is a system that is created by the synthetic assembly of two or more materials; namely, a filler or reinforcing element and a compatible resin binder to obtain specific characteristics and properties. Normally, the components of the composites can be physically identified along with the interface between components and, as such, plywood is also termed as a composite product of wood and adhesive.

Wood polymer composite is a new kind of material produced by impregnating wood with a mono-

mer and polymerising the monomer by heat and pressure or with nuclear radiation or by the application of suitable catalyst^{49,50}. The incorporation of a polymer in wood markedly enhances its properties, such as hardness, dimensional stability, bending strength, impact resistance etc. without destroying the attractive features of wood. Methyl methacrylate and styrene monomers have been used for impregnation.

Work on fire-retardant wood-polymer composite has been discussed in the recent literature by the author⁵¹. Mixture of water soluble monomers, dimers and oligomers of amino resin salts of phosphoric acid is incorporated in the timber or plywood by vacuum-cum-pressure impregnation method and the same is polymerised in wood by thermocatalytic process to give a leach resistant, fire retardant wood polymer composite.

Densified wood laminates include composite material made from wood veneer impregnated with synthetic phenolic resin over a considerable range, and compressed to a greater or less degree. Densified wood is known under a variety of names, e.g. 'Laminated compressed wood', 'Compreg', 'Preg wood' etc. Large quantities of 'compreg' are used for jigs, press tools and dies with success, due to its great strength and hardness.

Conclusion

The uses of adhesives based on polymeric materials have reached a stage which would have been considered impossible even a few decades ago. But our knowledge of the fundamentals of the subject is still limited. Many theories of adhesion have been discussed, and mechanism of adhesion and factors that affect it have been put forward and yet many points in this complex phenomenon are to be clarified. Only the tip of the iceberg is visible but a lot is still to be known.

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